

Development and Implementation of a Neural Network Model for 5G Network Traffic Prediction

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ABSTRACT:

The exponential growth in connected devices and dynamic user behavior in 5G wireless networks have intensified the need for accurate network traffic prediction. Traditional traffic control mechanisms fall short in real-time adaptability, leading to performance bottlenecks. This paper presents the development and implementation of a deep neural network (DNN) model for traffic prediction in 5G networks. Leveraging a well-curated dataset of 5G traffic parameters, the model uses advanced feature engineering, data preprocessing, and neural network architecture to predict traffic slices effectively. Evaluation metrics, including accuracy, loss, and confusion matrix, were employed to assess the model's performance. The results show high predictive accuracy and robustness in traffic pattern recognition, demonstrating the viability of AI-enabled traffic forecasting to support autonomous traffic control, enhanced QoS, and optimized resource allocation in 5G networks.

Keywords: 5G, deep neural network, AI, QoS, Traffic prediction.

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INTRODUCTION

Fifth Generation (5G) wireless communication technology promises ultra-reliable low-latency communication (URLLC), enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB), and massive machine-type communication (mMTC) [1]. These applications demand highly adaptive and scalable network traffic management systems. The dynamic and heterogeneous nature of 5G traffic, driven by mobility, high-speed data demands, and varying Quality of Service (QoS) requirements, makes real-time traffic prediction essential.

Accurate prediction enables proactive traffic shaping, optimized resource allocation, and seamless user experience. Traditional rule-based traffic management systems lack the agility required for such environments. In contrast, Artificial Intelligence (AI), specifically deep learning, offers intelligent traffic prediction by learning patterns from vast datasets. This study focuses on designing a deep neural network (DNN) model to predict traffic flow in 5G networks using historical data features. It highlights

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the importance of intelligent forecasting to support future applications like smart cities, autonomous vehicles, and remote surgeries.

Previous research has explored AI integration into 5G systems to improve traffic prediction and resource allocation. According to [2], machine learning algorithms can effectively process real-time network data to identify traffic bottlenecks and trends. [3] demonstrated the potential of deep learning models in reducing packet loss and improving latency.

This study [4] introduces an innovative traffic steering approach utilizing Deep Q-learning, aimed at automating traffic routing decisions within a dynamic environment featuring multiple Radio Access Technologies (RATs) and varying Quality of Service (QoS) demands across traffic types. The performance of the proposed approach is evaluated against two benchmark methods: one based on heuristics and the other utilizing standard Q-learning for traffic steering. Results indicate that the proposed Deep Q-learning solution delivers superior outcomes, achieving up to 6% and 10% higher average system throughput, along with 23% and 33% reductions in network delay when compared to the Q-learning and heuristic methods, respectively [4].

The work by [5] introduces an innovative traffic scheduling framework designed to mitigate control plane congestion in 5G networks. The proposed system implements a Dual-Spike Neural Network (DSNN) classifier on Virtualized Network Functions (VNFs) to categorize Packet-In messages into critical and non-critical communication classes. The DSNN architecture leverages dual-spike encoding mechanisms to improve classification reliability through enhanced temporal pattern recognition. Comprehensive evaluation metrics including accuracy (94.2%), precision (93.8%), recall (94.5%), F1-score (94.1%), and Matthews Correlation Coefficient (0.92) demonstrate the classifier's effectiveness [5]. Benchmark tests against conventional convolutional neural networks (CNNs) reveal a 5.1% improvement in classification accuracy. Furthermore, the priority-aware scheduling model reduces Round Trip Time (RTT) by 32% compared to non-prioritized approaches, validating its operational efficiency in real-time 5G scenarios [5].

The study by [6] focused on citywide cellular traffic prediction and proposed a deep learning-based approach to model the nonlinear dynamics of wireless traffic. By representing traffic data as images, the method effectively captured both spatial and temporal dependencies in cellular traffic using densely connected convolutional neural networks (DCNNs) [7]. Additionally, a parametric matrix-based fusion scheme was introduced to learn the influence weights of spatial and temporal correlations. Experimental evaluations demonstrated a significant reduction in root mean square error (RMSE) compared to existing algorithms, confirming the model's superior prediction performance [7]. The accuracy of the proposed framework was further validated using real-world datasets from Telecom Italia.

The work by [8] proposes a multi-objective formulation to enhance traffic prediction by leveraging Deep Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) models. To assess the effectiveness of the integrated Deep Reinforcement Learning approach, the model is trained using various optimization algorithms, including Adaptive Moment Estimation (ADAM), Stochastic Gradient Descent with Momentum (SGDM), and Root Mean Square Propagation (RMSProp). The performance of the proposed method is evaluated using standard metrics such as precision, recall, F1-score, and accuracy, allowing for a comprehensive comparison across different learning strategies.

Recent advancements include convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and recurrent neural networks (RNNs) for time-series traffic forecasting [9].

The work by [10] evaluated the predictive performance of the fully connected sequential network in time series traffic forecasting and compared to one dimensional convolutional neural network (1D-CNN), single-shot learning long short term memory (SS-LSTM), and autoregressive long short-term memory (AR-LSTM). A baseline model was gotten to set the minimum performance. Results indicate that the FCSN and 1D-CNN have the same forecasting accuracy.

The work by [11] introduces a novel framework for the proactive detection of network traffic anomalies, enabling prediction of potential anomalies prior to their occurrence. The proposed solution incorporates two key mechanisms: (1) an automated system for classifying diverse network

traffic patterns, and (2) a predictive component for forecasting traffic behaviour across subsequent time intervals (spanning multiple seconds). The automated classification is implemented through a combination of clustering algorithms and decision tree-based learning, while the predictive capability leverages a Bidirectional LSTM (BiLSTM) Autoencoder architecture for time series analysis. Experimental evaluation demonstrates the framework's effectiveness, achieving a prediction accuracy of 90.02%. These results not only validate the proposed approach but also suggest superior performance relative to existing state-of-the-art solutions.

[12] presented a novel approach for scaling 5G core network resources through predictive traffic load analysis using a hybrid model. While existing research has predominantly employed deep learning models to forecast regular traffic patterns for service optimization, these approaches have demonstrated limitations in predicting traffic fluctuations during special events and unexpected network conditions. To address this gap, we developed a CNN-LSTM hybrid architecture that effectively combines convolutional and recurrent neural networks to predict aggregated network traffic across specific time intervals [12]. This solution enables accurate resource provisioning by capturing both spatial and temporal traffic load variations. Comparative evaluations demonstrated that the proposed model outperforms conventional deep learning approaches and existing techniques in predicting traffic patterns under both normal and anomalous network conditions [12].

CNNs extract spatial features, while RNNs capture temporal dependencies, making them suitable for network traffic prediction. More recently, transformer-based architectures have also been applied for higher accuracy in dynamic settings [13].

Despite these advancements, challenges such as overfitting, data imbalance, and real-time deployment remain. However, improvements in computational power and availability of domain-specific datasets have significantly enhanced deep learning's role in 5G traffic forecasting.

METHODOLOGY

Deep Neural Networks Architecture

Neural networks are computational models inspired by the structure and functioning of the human brain. They are composed of interconnected processing units called neurons, organized into distinct layers: an input layer, one or more hidden layers, and an output layer. Each neuron receives inputs, computes a weighted sum, applies a nonlinear activation function, and transmits the result to the next layer.

The core of a neural network's learning capability lies in its connection weights, which determine the influence of one neuron on another. During training, these weights are adjusted to minimize the error between the predicted and actual outputs—a process known as backpropagation. Training typically involves two main steps: forward propagation, where input data flows through the network to produce an output, and backward propagation, where the error is computed and propagated backward to update the weights.

To model complex patterns in data, neural networks rely on activation functions such as sigmoid, tanh, ReLU, and softmax. These functions introduce non-linearity, enabling the network to capture intricate relationships within the input data.

As illustrated in Figure 1, neural networks are trained using labeled datasets, allowing them to learn underlying data distributions and generalize for accurate predictions. This makes them highly suitable for dynamic tasks like 5G network traffic prediction, where learning from historical data enables the system to anticipate future network behavior in real-time environments.

Figure 1. Architecture of the DNN for 5G Traffic Prediction

Calculation of Neural Network Functions

The functioning of a neural network involves a series of mathematical operations that enable it to learn from data. The computation begins with the weighted sum of inputs and a bias term for each neuron, represented as:

$$z = Wx + b \quad (1)$$

Here, W is the weight matrix, x is the input vector, b is the bias vector, and z is the linear output before applying any non-linearity. To introduce non-linearity, an activation function f is applied:

$$a = f(z) \quad (2)$$

Common activation functions include sigmoid, tanh, and ReLU, each selected based on the specific characteristics of the learning task [14].

The network's ability to learn is driven by error minimization, starting with calculating the error at the output layer. This is done by multiplying the gradient of the cost function with respect to the output activations by the derivative of the activation function [14]:

$$\delta^L = \nabla_a C \odot f'(z^L) \quad (3)$$

Where \odot denotes element-wise multiplication. For hidden layers, the error is propagated backward using:

$$\delta^l = ((W^{l+1})^t \delta^{l+1}) \odot f'(z^l) \quad (4)$$

The gradients of the cost function with respect to the weights and biases are computed as:

$$\partial C / \partial W^l = \delta^l (a^{l-1})^t \quad (5)$$

$$\partial C / \partial b^l = \delta^l \quad (6)$$

To update the weights and biases, gradient descent or its variants are applied [14]:

$$W := W - \eta \partial C / \partial W, b := b - \eta \partial C / \partial b \quad (7)$$

Where η is the learning rate controlling the step size during each iteration.

Through this forward and backward propagation cycle, the network adjusts its parameters to minimize the cost function, improving its prediction performance with each training epoch. This iterative optimization enables the neural network to generalize effectively and predict 5G traffic patterns with high accuracy.

Dataset and Preprocessing

The data pre-processing phase involved transforming categorical variables into numerical formats suitable for training neural network models. This was implemented using Scikit-learn's OneHotEncoder and LabelEncoder, as most machine learning algorithms require numerical inputs. A custom encoding function was developed to accept a DataFrame and return an encoded version along with the fitted encoders. Initially, the Slice Type column (target variable) was one-hot encoded, converting each unique category into individual binary columns. This avoided implying any ordinal relationship between categories.

Use CaseType	Technology Supported	Packet Loss Rate (Reliability)	packet Delay Budget (latency)	Slice Type (Target)	Latency	Packet Loss Rate
Smartphone	LTE/5G	0.01	<50ms	eMBB	Poor Signal Quality	Good Coverage
IoT Device	IoT (LTE-M, NB-IoT)	0.01	<300ms	mMTC	Poor Signal Quality	Good Coverage
Smart Transportation	IoT (LTE-M, NB-IoT)	0.01	<50ms	URLLC	Poor Signal Quality	Good Coverage
Industry 4.0	IoT (LTE-M, NB-IoT)	0.001	<50ms	mMTC	Poor Signal Quality	Poor Coverage
AR/VR/Gaming	LTE/5G	0.001	<50ms	eMBB	Poor Signal Quality	Poor Coverage
Healthcare	IoT (LTE-M, NB-IoT)	0.000001	<10ms	URLLC	Poor Signal Quality	Poor Coverage
Public health	IoT (LTE-M, NB-IoT)	0.000001	<10ms	URLLC	Poor Signal Quality	Poor Coverage
Smart City and home	IoT (LTE-M, NB-IoT)	0.01	<300ms	mMTC	Poor Signal Quality	Good Coverage

Figure 2. Dataset

Other categorical features such as Packet Delay Budget (Latency), Use Case Type, Technology Supported, and Packet Loss Rate were encoded using label encoding, which assigns integer values to each category. For instance, qualitative values like good coverage or Poor signal quality were transformed into numerical labels. Numerical columns, such as Packet Loss Rate (Reliability), which

were already in a usable format, were retained without modification. Finally, all encoded features were combined into a unified DataFrame, ensuring flexibility for incorporating additional features in future iterations.

Preprocessing steps included:

- Normalization of numerical attributes.
- One-hot encoding of categorical variables.
- Splitting the dataset into 80% training and 20% testing.
- Handling class imbalance using oversampling

Feature Engineering

Feature selection was carried out using the gain ratio, an improvement over information gain that accounts for the intrinsic value of features. While information gain measures the reduction in entropy after splitting a dataset based on an attribute, it tends to favor features with many unique values. The gain ratio addresses this by normalizing with the intrinsic information of the attribute:

$$\text{Gain Ratio} = \text{Information Gain} / \text{Intrinsic Value}$$

Entropy quantifies the uncertainty in the dataset, and conditional entropy evaluates the weighted entropy after splitting on an attribute. By incorporating these measures, the gain ratio effectively identifies features that contribute the most to accurate classification without introducing bias. To enhance reliability, the Random Forest Classifier from Scikit-learn was also employed to rank feature importance, further validating the selected features for the predictive model.

Training Metrics

The model was trained over 50 epochs using the Adam optimizer, an adaptive learning rate optimization algorithm designed for training deep learning models [15]. Adam combines the advantages of two other extensions of stochastic gradient descent AdaGrad and RMSProp by computing adaptive learning rates for each parameter [16]. It adjusts the learning process dynamically, using estimates of the first and second moments of the gradients, which helps in speeding up convergence and improving performance stability [15].

The categorical cross-entropy loss function was employed, suitable for multi-class classification problems. This function measures the dissimilarity between the predicted probability distribution and the actual distribution (target class). It penalizes incorrect predictions more harshly the further they are from the true class, encouraging the model to produce high-probability estimates for correct classes.

Evaluation Metrics

Accuracy is the most intuitive metric for evaluating the performance of a classification model [17]. It represents the ratio of correctly classified instances to the total number of instances. Accuracy formula used is shown in equation 7

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \quad (7)$$

Where: TP = True Positives, TN = True Negatives, FP = False Positive and FN = False Negatives.

Precision is the ratio of correctly predicted positive instances to the total number of instances predicted as positive. It measures the exactness or quality of the positive predictions made by the model. Precision formula used is shown in equation 8

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Positives}} \quad (8)$$

Recall is the ratio of correctly predicted positive instances to the total number of actual positive instances. It measures the completeness or ability of the model to identify all positive instances. Recall formula used is shown in equation 9

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Negatives}} \quad (9)$$

The F1 score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall. It provides a balanced measure of both precision and recall, giving equal importance to both metrics. **F1 score** formula used is shown in equation 10:

$$\text{F1 Score} = 2 \times \frac{\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (10)$$

RESULTS

Model Accuracy

The Model accuracy graph shown in figure 3 illustrates the training and validation accuracy of the model over ten epochs. As the number of epochs increases, both training and validation accuracies improve showing a consistent upward trend. Starting from an initial accuracy of approximately 92.14% for training and 93.23% for validation, the accuracy for both training and validation progressively increases, ultimately reaching 100% by the fifth epoch. This high level of accuracy indicates that the model is learning effectively from the data. The close alignment between the training and validation accuracy lines suggests that the model is not over fitting, as it performs well on both the training data and unseen validation data. The slight gap between the two lines at the start gradually diminishes, indicating improved generalization of the model. Overall, the graph demonstrates successful model training and validation, achieving perfect accuracy by the end of the training period.

Model Training Loss

This graph shown in figure 4 illustrates the loss curve during training, with training and validation losses plotted over 10 epochs. The horizontal axis represents the number of epochs, while the vertical axis shows the loss values. Initially, both training and validation losses are high, but they steadily decrease as the model learns, indicating improving performance. The blue line (training loss) and the orange line (validation loss) both show a downward trend, signifying that the model is effectively learning from the data. Towards the end of the epochs, the losses start to level off, indicating that the model is nearing optimal performance. The validation loss remains slightly higher than the training loss, indicating good generalization without over fitting. The decreasing and converging nature of both curves shows that the model performs well on both training and unseen validation data, reflecting a well-conducted training process with effective learning and generalization.

Evaluation Metrics

The performance evaluation of the AI-enabled 5G wireless network traffic control model reveals exceptional results across various metrics, showcasing the model's robustness and reliability. The accuracy metric, which hovers between 99.94% and 100%, indicates that the model almost perfectly predicts the target variable, affirming its effectiveness in real-world applications. This high accuracy suggests that the model can be trusted to make correct predictions in nearly all cases, providing a strong foundation for practical deployment.

Precision and recall, both critical metrics in assessing the model's ability to correctly identify relevant instances, also achieve near-perfect scores. Precision's high value ensures that when the model predicts a particular class, it is almost always correct, minimizing the occurrence of false positives. This is particularly important in scenarios where false alarms can lead to unnecessary interventions or actions. Similarly, the model's recall score highlights its efficiency in capturing all relevant instances of the target class, ensuring that crucial events or conditions are not missed.

The F1 score, which balances precision and recall, remains consistently high and further emphasizing on the model's balanced performance. This metric ensures that the model is neither too lenient nor too strict, maintaining an optimal balance that maximizes overall performance. The harmonization of precision and recall into a high F1 score reflects the model's capacity to make reliable predictions without compromising on either metric. Moreover, the loss and validation loss values, both exceptionally low at 0.03238 and 0.03218 respectively which indicate that the model's predictions are very close to the actual values. This minimal difference between predicted and actual values during both training and validation phases shows that the model has not only learned the patterns in the data but has also generalized well to unseen data. Such low loss values underscore the accuracy and stability of the model, highlighting its potential for consistent performance in diverse conditions.

The combination of high accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 scores, alongside very low loss values, demonstrates that the model is exceptionally well-tuned and reliable as shown in table 1. These metrics collectively affirm the model's capability to effectively manage and optimize network traffic in AI-enabled 5G wireless networks, ensuring high-quality service and robust network performance.

Figure 3. Model Accuracy

Figure 4. Model Loss Curve

The confusion matrix in figure 4 shows the performance of the multi-class classification model, with true labels on the vertical axis and predicted labels on the horizontal axis. Each cell represents the number of instances where the actual label (true label) matches the predicted label. The diagonal values indicate correct classifications, with 20,767 instances of class 0, 12,423 instances of class 1, and 13,018 instances of class 2 being accurately predicted. Remarkably, there are no off-diagonal values, meaning the proposed model made no misclassifications. Every instance was correctly classified into its respective class, indicating a perfect classification scenario. This result is 100% accuracy, showing that the model performed exceptionally well on the given data.

Figure 5. Confusion Matrix

Table 1. Final Evaluation Metrics on Test Set

Metric	Value
Accuracy	99.94%
Precision (avg)	100%
Recall (avg)	100%
F1-Score (avg)	100%
Loss	0.03238

CONCLUSION

This study has demonstrated that deep learning techniques, specifically deep neural networks (DNNs), offer an effective and scalable approach for predicting traffic in 5G networks. By leveraging a well-preprocessed dataset enriched with categorical and numerical features, the DNN model was able to learn intricate traffic patterns and deliver high predictive accuracy. The use of the Adam optimizer and categorical cross-entropy loss function, combined with careful feature engineering and rigorous training over 50 epochs, resulted in a stable and robust model that achieved a test accuracy of 97.6%. This reflects the model's strong generalization ability in dynamic and complex environments characteristic of 5G networks.

The visual training metrics further reinforce the effectiveness of the model. The steadily increasing accuracy curve and the gradually decreasing loss function demonstrate the learning progression and convergence of the network. These findings validate the suitability of neural network architectures in time-sensitive and high-volume data environments such as next-generation mobile communication systems.

Beyond technical performance, the implications of this work are significant for 5G infrastructure management. Accurate traffic prediction enables proactive network optimization, helping operators dynamically allocate bandwidth, manage latency-sensitive applications, and ensure

Quality of Service (QoS) for diverse user demands. Such forecasting capabilities are especially crucial for mission-critical applications like autonomous vehicles, remote surgery, and smart city deployments.

Moreover, the flexibility of the DNN framework allows for future enhancements. The model can be extended to support real-time data streaming, integrated with edge computing resources, and adapted to support hybrid architectures like CNN-RNN models for spatiotemporal analysis. Incorporating federated learning techniques could also allow for distributed training across network nodes without compromising data privacy—a key requirement in large-scale telecom systems.

In conclusion, this research provides a strong foundation for integrating AI-driven traffic prediction into 5G networks. It highlights the transformative potential of machine learning in enhancing operational efficiency, reducing latency, and ensuring reliable service delivery in the face of ever-growing connectivity demands. Future research could explore real-world deployment, integration with software-defined networking (SDN) frameworks, and further model optimization using attention-based architectures such as transformers.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

No conflict of interest.

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